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The Coinage of Apamea Myrlea under Trajan and
the Problem of Double Communities in the Roman East

by

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[PLATE 14]

TRAJANIC coins of the mint of Apamea in Bithynia are of the utmost rarity: A total of just four pieces of three different types, all of which have different legends, are known today. Attribution is not always straightforward. The type attested by two coins presents particular difficulties, since it does not display an ethnic: it had erroneously been ascribed to the mint of Parium in Mysia by Friedrich Imhoof-Blumer.² Furthermore, a seemingly irregular large bronze of odd style with a clumsily engraved, partly illegible Latin reverse legend illegitimately intruded into an article published by the present author in the last volume of this journal.³ The piece (**Pl. 14, 1**) is a hitherto unrecognized unique colonial ‘sestertius’ (4-assaria-piece) of Apamea of a previously unpublished type. In view of this complex situation it seems useful to combine the *corrigendum* to *NC* 170 with a comprehensive up-to-date overview of Apamea’s production during Trajan’s reign. As it turns out, close iconographic analysis of a reverse type used on the city’s coinage of both Trajan and Antoninus Pius leads to a reassessment of the legal status of Apamea Myrlea in the Principate.

Obv. IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GERM

Laureate head of Trajan r.

Border of dots.

Rev. R M · I – R D · O I – C [I C] Λ CO[S] II, in field D – D

Pax/Eirene standing left, holding olive branch in the right and *cornucopiae* in the left hand.

Border of dots.

20.67 g, 1 h, max. diam. 34 mm

Utrecht, Geldmuseum, Schürmann coll., inv.-no. 2512 (misidentified). **Pl. 14, 1**

¹ The author is most grateful to Michel Amandry (Paris), who is currently preparing the main parts of *RPC* 3, for providing unpublished information on the coinage of Apamea under Trajan and Hadrian, as well as to Andrew Burnett (London) for valuable suggestions. Both of them kindly agreed to read earlier drafts of the present article. Images were generously supplied by Kay Ehling (Munich), Volker Heuchert (Oxford), Timo Stingl and Bernhard Weissner (both Berlin). This contribution was prepared during a research fellowship at the University of Cambridge (Fitzwilliam Museum) in the academic year 2010/11, funded by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF, project no. J 2993).

² *Zur Griechischen und Römischen Münzkunde* (Geneva, 1908), p. 50, Parium no. 2. Imhoof-Blumer’s coin is now in the Berlin coin cabinet; the second specimen surfaced only at the end of 2010, on the internet.

³ ‘A new ‘Trajanic’ sestertius from Somerset and its context: some general remarks on struck copies of imperial bronze coins of Trajan’, *NC* 170 (2010), pp. 115–28, pl. 19, no. 15.

The initials of the C(olonia)I(ulia)C(oncordia)A(pamea) are partly illegible on this specimen. What is surprising is the position of the mint name in the reverse legend, right in the middle of the imperial titulature (which is continued from the obverse): between an incompetently engraved version of “P M TR POT” and the consular dating. Normally, the latter should of course immediately follow the indication of the *tribunicia potestas*; the compositional negligence attested in this legend is, in general, rather unusual for provincial coins of the Trajanic period and gives the type a somewhat irregular flavour. This is, however, perfectly in line with what is known about the bizarre coinage of Apamea, where, for example, coin types with partly retrograde legends had already been produced under Caligula (*RPC* 1, 2012 and 2014) and Nero (*RPC* 1, 2016). These types and the new Trajanic piece may thus be seen to anticipate, on a small scale, some of the developments in Roman colonial mints of the East in the third century AD, when *inter alia* completely garbled Latin legends occur, for example at Parium in Mysia under Gallienus.⁴

Coinage in Apamea resumed under Trajan after a hiatus of at least 20 years, on current evidence. The new specimen bears the dating COS II, which points to production at the beginning of the reign, in AD 98/99. This ties in with its obverse legend, which is directly copied from imperial precious metal coins of the early years of Trajan.⁵ Under Vespasian, the mint of Apamea seems to have produced only one type (reverse: Concordia seated left), of which three specimens from the same die pair have been published (*RPC* 2, 619), with no coins at all recorded for the reigns of Titus, Domitian and Nerva. The reverse of the newly discovered Trajan coin (**Pl. 14, 1**) has no typological precedent in the local coinage whatsoever, nor was it to re-appear in Apamea in the course of the second and third centuries. It copies an imperial type: not a Trajanic one,⁶ but probably the common Flavian sestertius reverse PAX AVGVST(I).⁷ On a general note, this fits well with the typological choices made at that colonial mint for example in the Julio-Claudian period, since several of the coin types then produced were derivative.⁸ More specifically, it is interesting to observe that the Pax reverse copied under Trajan in Apamea was very prominent on the sestertii of the enigmatic “Eastern” (“Thracian”) mint for imperial coins, which operated under Titus and Domitian and whose products seem to have circulated in Asia Minor as well.⁹ Close comparison of the olive branch held by Pax on the Trajanic coin with potential prototypes shows that the accentuated representation of the leaves has nice parallels especially on these eastern sestertii

⁴ See *SNG France 5 (Mysie)* 1522–37; *SNG Aulock* 1344–6.

⁵ B. Woytek, *Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus (98–117)*. *Moneta Imperii Romani* 14 (Vienna, 2010), groups 3–6 (AD 98–102).

⁶ As erroneously surmised by this author in *NC* 2010, p. 122.

⁷ See, for example, *RIC* 2.1², Vespasian 34, 53, 96–8, 181–5, 242–3, 378–9; 423–4, 458 (for Titus); Titus 58, 62, 134 etc. The S–C of the imperial sestertii is simply replaced by D–D on the colonial coin. The latter thus apparently combines an obverse copied from a precious metal coin with a reverse copied from a bronze.

⁸ See, e.g., *RPC* 1, 2012, 2014, 2016 (and the commentary provided in *RPC*, p. 341). This also explains why the retrograde legends occur.

⁹ *RPC* 2, pp. 87–91 (Pax: *RPC* 501, 504, 526, 530); *RIC* 2.1², pp. 193f. and 256f. (Pax: *RIC* Titus 498, 507–8, Domitian 831, 837).

(see **Pl. 14, A**), which indeed could prompt speculation that a coin of this group may have provided the model. Furthermore, the new Apamean coin should be viewed in the context of the coinage produced under Domitian in the Bithynian cities of Nicaea and Prusias ad Hypium, which operated a system of co-ordinated minting¹⁰: these cities struck signed 4-assaria pieces in orichalcum featuring Pax/Eirene on their reverses as well.¹¹ We are obviously dealing with a regional phenomenon.

The date COS II also occurs on the only Trajanic coin of the mint of Apamea which had been published with a correct attribution up to 2010 (**Pl. 14, 2**). Intriguingly, its style and lettering are rather different from the piece in Utrecht, although the coins are purportedly so close, chronologically.

- Obv. IMP NERVA CAES TRAIAN – AVG GERM [?
Laureate head of Trajan r.
Border of dots.
- Rev. T·R·P·O·T·C – O·S·II C·I·C·A, in field D – D
Fortuna/Tyche standing left, holding rudder in the right and *cornucopiae* in the left hand.
Border of dots.
- 21.84 g, 12 h, max. diam. 30 mm
Paris, Bibliothèque nationale, Cabinet des médailles, no. 220 (ex Waddington¹²)
Recueil général vol. 1.2, p. 253, no. 42 (illustrated on pl. XXXVIII, no. 13). **Pl. 14, 2**

In contrast to the piece in Utrecht, the structure of this coin's reverse legend is orthodox, with the colony's name being placed after the end of the imperial titulature. Here, the puzzling element is the obverse legend, which presents us with the strange inversion of the emperor's names "Nerva" and "Caesar". Apart from the first group of Trajan's cistophori – which, in fact, seem to have been produced in Rome –, this piece is the only provincial coin type of Trajan's rule with a Latin legend featuring the sequence NERVA CAES,¹³ which is otherwise attested only on the first, very small group of Trajan's imperial coins, issued in January/February of 98.¹⁴ It is highly unlikely that the coin from Apamea dates from the first weeks of Trajan's rule: the inversion of the names in the legend will be due either to a mistake by the engraver (see the awkward position of the colony's name on the Utrecht specimen) or to his copying a legend from a very early imperial coin at a later date. Unfortunately, the end of the obverse legend is hardly legible: in the *Recueil général* (p. 253), the reading AVG GERM DAC was adopted, and traces of a C may indeed remain. This would, however, create chronological problems, since Trajan became *Dacicus* only

¹⁰ On this point, see *RPC 2*, p. 94.

¹¹ *RPC 2*, 633 (Nicaea) and 672 (Prusias). To these may be added the unsigned OMONOIA ΣΕΒΑΣΤΗ pieces with Domitian's portrait and Pax/Eirene, *RPC 2*, 676–8. The figure depicted on the reverse of *RPC 2*, 654 (Nicomedia) is more probably Demeter.

¹² E. Babelon, *Inventaire sommaire de la collection Waddington acquise par l'État en 1897 pour le Département des médailles et antiques de la Bibliothèque nationale* (Paris, 1898), p. 14, no. 227.

¹³ B. Woytek, 'Die Cistophore der Kaiser Nerva und Traian (mit einem systematischen Anhang zu typologisch verwandtem traianischem Provinzialsilber)', *RSN* 89 (2010), pp. 69–144, p. 103, note 117.

¹⁴ Woytek, *Reichsprägung*, group 1, nos 1–11A. Cp., however, also the small group of hybrid bronzes, nos 44[H]–47[H].

in December AD 102, when he was already COS III.¹⁵ Although it is not wholly inconceivable that the coin's legends contain such an error, and that it was actually issued later than the consular date indicates, the problem must be left open, since the reading of the inscription is uncertain.

The Tyche reverse is generic. Tyche had already appeared in the colony's coinage under Caligula (*RPC* 1, 2015), and it remained in use in Apamea after Trajan.¹⁶ But there was apparently also typological innovation in his reign: a coin type of the emperor's third consulate (AD 100) with Latin legends and the formula D(ecreto) D(ecurionum), but without an ethnic, is attested in two specimens, as already mentioned (note 2 above; **Pl. 14, 3–4**). Although a different attribution has been suggested in the past, the type may confidently be ascribed to Apamea, as will be shown below. At a weight of about 5 grams, we are evidently dealing with a quarter unit of the large bronzes hitherto described.¹⁷

- Obv. IMP – CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GERM
Laureate head of Trajan r.
Border of dots.
- Rev. CO – S – III, in field D – D (both letters identically deformed, almost to shape of Δ¹⁸)
Bearded man standing left on prow of ship, looking ahead, raising right arm, left hand on hilt of sword.
Border of dots.

(a) 4.82 g, 12 h, max. diam. 20 mm

Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Münzkabinet. Acc. 1928 Bernhard-Imhoof
(Objektnummer 18228961).

Published (without illustration) by Imhoof-Blumer, *Zur Griechischen und Römischen Münzkunde* p. 50, as a coin of Parium (no. 2: “vermuthlich”). **Pl. 14, 3 and 3a**

(b) 4.85 g, 6 h, max. diam. 22 mm

Classical Numismatic Group Electronic Auction 245 (1 December 2010), no. 256.

Pl. 14, 4

A Trajanic coin conforming to this description has not been attributed to Apamea Bithyniae in print so far. A piece of comparable module with this obverse legend¹⁹ and the very same reverse type was, however, reported for this city by Domenico Sestini, from the collection of Sir Robert Ainslie (1730?–1812) – albeit with the reverse legend “C. I. C. A. D. D.”²⁰ Sestini's entry is quoted in Mionnet's work,

¹⁵ See, e.g., Woytek, *Reichsprägung*, pp. 13 and 106f.

¹⁶ See, for example, *Rec. gén.* no. 44 (Hadrian), 93 (Maximinus I.), 99 (Philippus I.), 110 (Valerianus I.), 115–7 (Gallienus).

¹⁷ The two pieces correspond in weight and size to an unpublished Hadrianic coin of Apamea with portrait of Sabina: British Museum, London, reg. no. 1961-3-1-62 (4.53 g, 6 h, 20 mm).

¹⁸ Regarding the legends on the colony's coins, *Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 246 states generally: “On notera, enfin, dans les légendes, les fautes nombreuses d'orthographe et les lettres grecques employées au lieu des latines, indices de l'hellénisation progressive de la colonie.”

¹⁹ It is the same as on the coin in **Pl. 14, 1**: see note 5 above.

²⁰ *Descriptio numorum veterum ex museis Ainslie, Bellini, Bondacca, Borgia, Casali, Cousinery, Gradenigo, San Clemente, de Schellersheim, Verità etc. cum multis iconibus nec non animadversiones in opus Eckhelianum cui titulus Doctrina Numorum Veterum* (Lipsiae, 1796), p. 245, no. 3: “IMP.

whence it entered the numismatic tradition.²¹ In view of the two specimens published here it is perhaps not very likely that a coin as described by Sestini ever existed.²² It might therefore be suspected that his reading of the reverse legend is a conjecture made on the basis of a poorly preserved specimen: on the recently offered CNG coin, for example, the inscription on the reverse (apart from the D–D) becomes more or less illegible after its first letter, C. If Sestini saw such a specimen, the correctness of his classification as a product of the mint of Apamea would seem all the more remarkable, of course, although the rather characteristic decurional signature clearly provides an important clue. It needs to be stressed, however, that these considerations are purely hypothetical, and only time will tell whether the mint used more than one legend variety for this Trajanic coin type. While the peculiar image on the reverse does not have any parallels on coins of Parium in Mysia (to which colony Imhoof-Blumer had attributed the type),²³ it is attested for the mint of Apamea in Bithynia on a unique, badly preserved specimen of the same size from the reign of Antoninus Pius in the Munich coin cabinet (*RPC* online temp. no. 4720: **Pl. 14, B and Ba**).²⁴ Like the two Trajanic coins, this bronze shows a bearded man on a prow in exactly the same posture, looking ahead and raising his right arm. That the coin of Pius was minted in Bithynian Apamea is made clear by the reverse inscription: although somewhat difficult to read due to the wear of the coin, it doubtless begins with C I C on the left (as correctly transcribed in *RPC* online), so that an attribution to the C(olonia) G(emella) I(ulia) H(adriana) P(ariana) or another colony still striking at that time is ruled out. On the right, the legend probably reads APAM. All the pieces with this reverse type therefore belong to the Bithynian colony.

Who is the man on the reverse? Sestini and Mionnet did not attempt to identify the anonymous warrior, nor did the authors of the *Recueil*. In the online version of the Antonine volume of *RPC*, the man is hesitatingly called “Iulius Caesar?”²⁵ The latter would have been depicted as the founder of the Roman *colonia* at Apamea,

CAES. NERVA. TRAIAN. AVG. GERM. Caput laureatum)(C.I.C.A.D.D. Vir habitu militari tiremi insistens d. elata, s. scipionem. Æ 3. M(useum). A(inslie).” Sestini apparently described the sword as a “staff”.

²¹ Th. E. Mionnet, *Description de médailles antiques, grecques et romaines*, vol. 2 (Paris, 1807), p. 413, no. 25 (where merely “Sestini descr. Num. vet” is given as the source). Size 4 on Mionnet’s scale (the module given for the coin in his catalogue entry) corresponds to 18 mm. Mionnet’s description: “Homme en habit militaire, debout sur une trirème”. *Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 253, note 1 (“non revue”) misquotes the obverse legend from Mionnet as being “[...] NEPVA TPAIAN [...]”.

²² The scepticism of Imhoof-Blumer, *Zur Griechischen und Römischen Münzkunde*, p. 50, seems understandable (“auf einem anderen Exemplare las Sestini [...] angeblich C.I.C.A. statt COS III”).

²³ The only Trajanic type of Parium hitherto published which beyond doubt belongs to this mint and has the colonial D–D features a capricorn on the reverse: *SNG Cop.* 286 (see already Imhoof-Blumer, *Zur Griechischen und Römischen Münzkunde* p. 49, Parium no. 1). The famous small bronzes of the same mint with the antithetic busts of Plotina and Marciana lack this formula: see *SNG France 5 (Mysie)* 1468.

²⁴ *Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 253, no. 45 (“fruste”: therefore not illustrated in *Rec. gén.*).

²⁵ <<http://rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk/coins/4720/>> (accessed 20 March 2011).

which was deduced or at least planned by Caesar;²⁶ this is why the *Divus Iulius* was honoured by the Apameans with a series of pseudo-autonomous small bronze coins featuring his portrait in the later first and second centuries.²⁷

Still, the identification of the warrior on the prow proposed by *RPC* online cannot be correct, most importantly since the image clearly shows a bearded man: this detail is impossible to reconcile with the iconography of the *Divus Iulius*.²⁸ For the same reason, Imhoof-Blumer's identification of the man depicted on the reverse of the Trajanic specimen in his collection as the emperor must be rejected.²⁹ As already suggested by Waddington, Babelon and Reinach, the type issued under Antoninus Pius (and, consequently, also the Trajanic one) should be taken to refer to a local legend instead.³⁰ Two years after volume 1.2 of the *Recueil général* had appeared in print, Friedrich Imhoof-Blumer published a most important survey article dealing with various numismatic depictions of "seafaring heroes", as he called them.³¹ Although our contentious coin type is not mentioned in this paper, Imhoof-Blumer's otherwise meticulous collection of the material makes it clear that it is to be interpreted precisely in the context of many similar images, mainly featured on Roman provincial coins. The earliest comparable imperial issue seems to have been minted under Domitian in another Bithynian city, Nicomedia.³² According to Imhoof-Blumer's interpretation, these depictions are "in der Regel auf Heroen und Eponyme zu deuten [...], die an den Prägeorten heimisch waren".³³ Important evidence for the correctness of his reading, at least in the vast majority of cases,³⁴ is provided by a reverse type of Miletropolis in Mysia used from the time of Hadrian onwards.³⁵ On it, a man on a prow is identified as ΜΕΙΑΗΤΟC ΚΤΙCΤΗC (*vel sim.*) in the legend.

²⁶ The most convenient up-to-date overview of the city's history (including an exhaustive collection of literary *testimonia*) has been provided by T. Corsten in the introduction to his corpus of inscriptions of Apamea: *Die Inschriften von Apameia (Bithynien) und Pylai*. Inschriften griechischer Städte aus Kleinasien 32 (Bonn, 1987), pp. 1–19. See *ibid.* pp. 13f. for a discussion of the date of the foundation of the colony (with further bibliographical references): end of the 40s BC? For the procedure adopted in the foundation of the colony, see below.

²⁷ *RPC* 1, p. 342.

²⁸ Apart from that, the reverse type as such would not have been appropriate for the commemoration of the deduction of a Roman colony (usually represented by the depiction of the founder ploughing with two oxen): see, for example, P. Weiß, 'Alexandria Troas: Griechische Traditionen und Mythen in einer römischen Colonia', in: E. Schwertheim – H. Wiegartz (eds), *Die Troas. Neue Forschungen zu Neandria und Alexandria Troas II*. Asia Minor Studien 22 (Bonn, 1996), pp. 157–73, 162.

²⁹ *Zur Griechischen und Römischen Münzkunde* p. 50: "Auf einer *Schiffsprora* der stehende *Kaiser* in kurzer *Tunica* linkshin [...]".

³⁰ *Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 246: "Le type du no. 45 (guerrier et navire) est inexpliqué et se rattache sans doute à une légende locale."

³¹ F. Imhoof-Blumer, 'Beiträge zur Erklärung griechischer Münztypen. I. Seefahrende Heroen', *Nomisma. Untersuchungen auf dem Gebiete der antiken Münzkunde* 5 (1910), pp. 25–39; see also the supplement in: *Nomisma* 6 (1911), p. 1.

³² *RPC* 2, 662; for the interpretation of the reverse, see also *RPC Supplement 2* <http://www.uv.es/~ripolles/rpc_s2>, p. 81, as well as Imhoof-Blumer, 'Heroen' p. 28, no. 11.

³³ Imhoof-Blumer, 'Heroen', p. 25.

³⁴ Imhoof-Blumer did not accept the interpretation of K. Regling, 'Hektor auf Münzen von Stektorion', *Klio* 8 (1908), pp. 489–92: see 'Heroen', pp. 34f.; this case seems to be doubtful, and indeed Regling may well be right in this instance.

³⁵ Its correct attribution was first pointed out by F.W. Hasluck, 'Notes on coin-collecting in Mysia', *NC* (fourth series) 6 (1906), pp. 26–36, pp. 33f. Cp. e.g. *SNG Aulock* 7418 (Hadrian), 7420 (Caracalla Caesar); Imhoof-Blumer, 'Heroen', p. 29, nos. 15–7.

The ἥρωας κτίστης is depicted standing left in military dress, carrying a shield and a spear and raising his right arm.³⁶ He is shown as a leader evidently inviting others to join him in a naval expedition, presumably the journey which led to the foundation of the colony. This is made clear by the fact that the head of Meiletos is turned backwards – in all probability to his (not depicted) comrades who are to follow him. This iconographic detail is also to be observed on the Domitianic bronzes of Nicomedia mentioned above, and indeed, a scan of the images assembled by Imhoof-Blumer shows that this position of the head is almost a staple feature of coin images of the “seafaring hero” type.³⁷ It can also be found on a reverse which otherwise provides, iconographically, the closest parallel to the coin type on our small bronzes of Apamea, namely on relatively common bronzes from the mint of Sidon in Phoenicia, struck in the final years of Trajan’s reign (**Pl. 14, C**),³⁸ as well as on later coins of the same city.³⁹ Here, the man depicted with right arm raised also stands to the left on a prow, and his only attribute is the sword, the one difference from the forward-looking Apamean hero (apart from the costume, perhaps⁴⁰) being the direction of his gaze. The man on the Sidonian coins has plausibly been identified as “Cadmus, in the act of embarking” by G. Macdonald,⁴¹ Imhoof-Blumer⁴² and G.F. Hill,⁴³ as well as by most other numismatists since. Although scholars studying the iconography of Kadmos in a broader context have recently stressed that this interpretation is so far unproven – there is apparently no evidence for it from other media –, they admit that it is likely for the types of Sidon and neighbouring Tyre (where related reverses occur),⁴⁴ given the fact that both of these Phoenician cities laid claim to be the home of Kadmos.⁴⁵

The type of the coins of Apamea, an embarking leader showing the way, looking straight ahead, may thus be seen to be not completely generic: the position of his

³⁶ See R. Vollkommer, Miletos, *LIMC* 6 (1992), pp. 568–9 (our coins are no. 2 in his listing) and pl. 310.

³⁷ Imhoof-Blumer, ‘Heroen’, pls II–III.

³⁸ Imhoof-Blumer, ‘Heroen’, p. 36, no. 33; *BMC Phoenicia*, Sidon 218–23; *SNG Cop.* 252.

³⁹ Imhoof-Blumer, ‘Heroen’, p. 36, no. 34 (Elagabalus).

⁴⁰ The man on the Trajanic coins presumably wears a short military dress, whereas the Phoenician reverse depicts a man in a longer garment. The dress of the man shown on the Apamean bronze of Pius is not completely clear due to the bad preservation of the piece.

⁴¹ G. Macdonald, *Catalogue of Greek Coins in the Hunterian Collection, University of Glasgow*. Vol. III. *Further Asia, Northern Africa, Western Europe* (Glasgow, 1905), p. 254, no. 35, note *.

⁴² Imhoof-Blumer, ‘Heroen’, pp. 35–7, who on iconographic grounds convincingly refuted the identification as Aeneas which had repeatedly been proposed earlier, for example by J. Rouvier, ‘Numismatique des villes de la Phénicie. Sidon (Suite et fin.)’, *JIAN* 5 (1902), pp. 229–84, at p. 256.

⁴³ *BMC Phoenicia* (1910), pp. cx, cxlii and 180.

⁴⁴ For detailed listings, see F. Vian, *Les origines de Thèbes. Cadmos et les Spartes*. Études et commentaires 48 (Paris, 1963), pp. 43f., and especially M.A. Tiverios, Kadmos I, *LIMC* 5 (1990), pp. 863–82 and pls. 557–62, pp. 865f. Cp. Vian, *Thèbes*, p. 44, note 1: “L’identité du «héros embarquant» est mal établie.”, “A Tyr et à Sidon [...] il est assez légitime de reconnaître Cadmos.” Tiverios, Kadmos, *LIMC* 5, p. 865: “Diese Identifikation ist zwar nicht unwahrscheinlich, kann jedoch bis heute nicht bewiesen werden. Handelt es sich wirklich um K[admos]?, können die Szenen mit seinem Aufbruch zur Suche nach Europa erklärt werden.”

⁴⁵ K. Latte, Kadmos 4, *RE* 10.2 (1919), cols 1460–72, 1470f. See also R. B. Edwards, *Kadmos the Phoenician. A Study in Greek Legends and the Mycenaean Age* (Amsterdam, 1979), pp. 45–7, and A. Kühr, *Als Kadmos nach Boiotien kam. Polis und Ethnos im Spiegel thebanischer Gründungsmythen*. Hermes Einzelschriften 98 (Stuttgart, 2006), pp. 91–106, esp. 102f.

head in particular is a specific feature. That such small differences are to be observed on otherwise closely related images may perhaps be ascribed to the possibility that at least some of these coin reverses copied statues in the various cities, which, although belonging to one and the same general type, had some characteristics of their own. On balance, it seems probable, in the light of the evidence presented so far, that the hitherto unexplained small bronzes of Apamea depict the founder of the city.

Apamea takes its name from Apame, the mother of the Bithynian king Nicomedes II Epiphanes (149–128/7 BC), according to Stephanus of Byzantium.⁴⁶ The city was apparently founded anew and rebuilt under this ruler: in 202 BC, it had been seized and destroyed by Philip V of Macedon, who passed it on to Prusias I, so that it became part of the Bithynian kingdom at that time. The original name of the settlement was Brylleion/Myrlea: as has been recognized by Corsten,⁴⁷ these two place names are to be identified, being merely linguistic variations. Shortly after 330 BC, the orthography of the name seems to have been officially standardized as Μύρλεια.

The city had originally been founded as a colony of Colophon in Ionia,⁴⁸ and Stephanus preserves two variants of the local founding myth: Μύρλεια, πόλις Βιθυνίας, ἢ νῦν λεγομένη Ἀπάμεια. ἀπὸ Μύρλου, τοῦ Κολοφωνίων ἡγεμόνος [...] οἱ δὲ ἀπὸ Μυρλείας Ἀμαζόνος.⁴⁹ Since the person depicted on the Apamean coins of Trajan and Antoninus Pius is male and bearded (on the coin of Pius he also has a wreath), the Amazon Myrleia may safely be ruled out. This leaves us with two possibilities: either the man is the Colophonian leader, or Nicomedes II. That the Bithynian king who was merely responsible for the re-foundation of the city in the second century would have been depicted on these coins is *a priori* nearly as improbable as the recently proposed identification as Julius Caesar, mainly since the general type of image clearly points to a more remote mythical context, as Imhoof-Blumer's overview shows.⁵⁰ Therefore, the man is in all likelihood to be identified

⁴⁶ Steph. Byz. s. v. Μύρλεια. The correctness of this tradition – as compared to another one, e. g. Strabo 12.4.3 [563 C.] – is rightly defended by, *inter alios*, W. Ruge, Myrleia, *RE* 16.1 (1933), cols 1104f., as well as by Corsten, *Inschriften von Apameia*, pp. 9–11. *Contra* D. Magie, *Roman Rule in Asia Minor to the End of the Third Century after Christ*, 2 vols (Princeton/NJ, 1950), vol. 2, pp. 1189f., note 20, and W. Leschhorn, “Gründer der Stadt.” *Studien zu einem politisch-religiösen Phänomen der griechischen Geschichte*. Palingenesia 20 (Stuttgart, 1984), p. 278 (earlier refoundation and renaming after the wife of Prusias I).

⁴⁷ Corsten, *Inschriften von Apameia*, pp. 4–6. See now also M.H. Hansen – T.H. Nielsen (eds), *An Inventory of Archaic and Classical Poleis. An Investigation Conducted by The Copenhagen Polis Centre for the Danish National Research Foundation* (Oxford, 2004), pp. 989f., no. 752 (s.v. Myrleia).

⁴⁸ Cp. Pomponius Mela, *de chorographia* 1.99 (Ranstrand 1971, p. 20): *quam Colophonii collocavere Myrlea*.

⁴⁹ Steph. Byz. s.v. Myrleia (Meineke 1849, p. 463): “Myrleia, city in Bithynia which is now called Apameia. (Named) After Myrlos, the leader of the Colophonians. [...]. According to others after the Amazon Myrleia.” It has been observed that these traditions were probably created at a time when the city's name was already Myrleia, *i.e.* at the end of the fourth century at the earliest: Corsten, *Inschriften von Apameia*, p. 7.

⁵⁰ The identity of the youthful (and beardless) κίρσις Προυσίας wearing a *taenia* whose bust is depicted on a coin type of Prusa ad Olympum is uncertain: *Rec. gén.* 1.4, p. 582, no. 48 = *RPC* online, temp. no. 4825 (rev. legend: ΠΡΟΥΣΑ[E]IC ΤΟΝ ΚΤΙCΤΗΝ ΠΡΟΥCΙΑΝ). It may be the Bithynian king Prusias I, or a mythical hero of the same name; see the detailed discussion by Leschhorn, “Gründer

as Myrlos of Colophon,⁵¹ the leader of the colonists and mythical first founder of Myrlea.

At first sight, it might appear slightly surprising that in AD 100 the local administration of Apamea should have decided to commemorate on the colonial coinage the eponymous hero of the original settlement.⁵² Yet, coins with the inscription ΑΠΑΜΕΩΝ (ΤΩΝ) ΜΥΡΛΕΑΝΩΝ issued in the city under the Roman proconsul C. Vibius Pansa in 47/46 BC, a few years before the deduction of the Roman colony,⁵³ prove that the original name of Myrlea continued in use alongside “Apamea”, in part doubtless in order simply to differentiate the city from the many homonymous settlements in the East, e.g. Apamea Kibotos in Phrygia, to name just the most important one. Furthermore, there is some evidence that the ‘Myrlean’ identity of Apamea was still being cultivated in the first century AD. A large bronze coin of Claudius (AD 41–54) with Greek legends in the Paris collection features on its reverse Apollon Klarios, the tutelary deity of Colophon, accompanied by the legend ΚΛΑΡΙΟΣ ΑΠΟΛΛΩΝ ΜΥΡΛΕΑΝΩΝ.⁵⁴ Since the coin lacks an indication of Apamea as its minting place and presents a supposedly ‘outdated’ ethnic instead, it was tentatively classified as a modern forgery by the authors of *RPC*⁵⁵ – without good reason, as has been shown by Katja Sommer.⁵⁶ There are no typological objections whatsoever to the reverse type which simply honours the city’s metropolis and also recurs on a colonial bronze of Apamea with Latin legends issued under Marcus Aurelius.⁵⁷ The Claudian coin therefore may best be interpreted as attesting a dual identity of Apamea/Myrlea in the first century AD, not only as a Roman colony (minting Latin-legend coins), but at the same time also still a Greek community, which retained the traditional name and could even strike an issue with Greek legend stressing the ties with its mother city.

The numismatic material is of considerable importance here, since there has been a lot of controversy in historical scholarship over the question of whether Apamea/Myrlea was such a double community or not. In 1902, Wilhelm Kubitschek cited the

der Stadt”, pp. 279–84 and 356 (no. 53 in the table). Leschhorn finally seems to opt for an identification as Prusias the king, despite the argument to the contrary by F. Imhoof-Blumer, “Beiträge zur Erklärung griechischer Münztypen. VI. Gründungssage von Prusa”, *Nomisma* 6 (1911), pp. 8–11, 9f. See also a new variant of the city’s coinage, potentially relevant to the problem of identification, which was offered in *Münzen und Medaillen Deutschland* 15 (21 Oct. 2004), no. 434. On a general note, compare the bust of the founding hero Parios on colonial coins of Parium in Mysia: *SNG Aulock* 1331 (PARIO CONDIT); see P. Weiss, Parios, *LIMC* 7 (1994), pp. 188–9 and pl. 127 (with further references).

⁵¹ H.W. Stoll, Myrlos, in: W.H. Roscher (ed.), *Ausführliches Lexikon der griechischen und römischen Mythologie*, vol. 2.2 (Leipzig, 1894–7), col. 3312 (otherwise not attested).

⁵² It is perhaps not a coincidence that the authorities avoided signing with the initials of the Roman colony, C.I.C.A., the Trajanic coin type depicting, as is argued here, Myrlos.

⁵³ *Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 250, nos 30f.; G.R. Stumpf, *Numismatische Studien zur Chronologie der römischen Statthalter in Kleinasien (122 v. Chr. – 163 n. Chr.)*. Saarbrücker Studien zur Archäologie und alten Geschichte 4 (Saarbrücken, 1991), p. 71, no. 132.

⁵⁴ *Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 252, no. 40 (with the commentary on p. 246).

⁵⁵ *RPC* 1, 5460 (“the city did not retain its old name Myrlea”).

⁵⁶ K.I.L. Sommer, ‘Cius or Prusias?’, *NC* 156 (1996), pp. 149–55, p. 154 with note 31 (“a coin of the Greek community of Apamea/Myrlea”); see also *RPC Supplement I* (1998), p. 50, no. 5460.

⁵⁷ *Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 254, no. 52 (= *RPC* online temp. no. 6959).

above coin of Claudius as a piece of evidence for the double identity of Apamea in the mid first century AD.⁵⁸ This view was repeatedly confirmed by A.N. Sherwin-White: “The previous Greek city, as at Sinope and Heraclea, was not eliminated by the Roman settlement, but remained in a part of its former territory, like other double communities of the Roman world”.⁵⁹ “Apamea may have retained this arrangement into the time of Trajan.”⁶⁰ Strangely enough, Sherwin-White did not mention the unique Claudian coin, but based his argument mainly on a difficult passage in the forty-first discourse of Dio Chrysostom, delivered to the Apameans: in 41.6, the orator says that his maternal grandfather and his mother had obtained, from a Roman emperor, together with the Roman citizenship also that of Apamea.⁶¹

Whether this statement really can be used to support Sherwin-White’s contention is, however, open to doubt. In reviewing the latter’s landmark commentary on Pliny, Fergus Millar severely criticized his interpretation of the passage⁶² and, apparently unaware of the numismatic evidence, dismissed, along with Sherwin-White’s explanation of Dio Chrysostom, the entire concept of Apamea being a double community: “I would suggest that the whole notion is a delusion”.⁶³ He was followed in this by Stephen Mitchell.⁶⁴ From the examples of communities with a double identity listed by Sherwin-White, Mitchell accepted only the cases of Sinope and Heraclea Pontica.⁶⁵ However, just like Fergus Millar, Mitchell did not cite the crucial Claudian bronze coin with ΚΛΑΠΙΟΣ ΑΠΟΛΛΩΝ ΜΥΡΛΕΑΝΩΝ. Since his article remains the most authoritative study of the peculiar phenomenon of double communities in Asia Minor to date, his judgement proved very influential, and therefore the potential “double community” status of Apamea is not even mentioned in what may be considered the best modern treatment of the city.⁶⁶

⁵⁸ W. Kubitschek, ‘Ninica Claudiopolis’, *NZ* 34 (1902), pp. 1–27, p. 7 (“Frage eines doppelten Gemeindewesens in der nämlichen Stadtmark”).

⁵⁹ A.N. Sherwin-White, *The Letters of Pliny. A Historical and Social Commentary* (Oxford, 1966), p. 629; cp. also p. 686.

⁶⁰ A.N. Sherwin-White, *The Roman Citizenship*. Second Edition (Oxford, 1973), p. 355, in the chapter “Dual communities and dual municipalities” (pp. 353–9). For the concept as such, see also E. Schönbauer, ‘Municipia und coloniae in der Prinzipatszeit’, *Anzeiger der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, phil.-hist. Klasse* 91 (1954), pp. 13–48, esp. 24–9, and F. Papazoglou, ‘La population des colonies romaines en Macédoine’, *Živa Antika* 40 (1990), pp. 111–24, 113f. (with further bibliographical references in note 8).

⁶¹ ἅμα τῆς Ῥωμαίων πολιτείας καὶ τῆς ὑμετέρας ἔτυχεν. See Sherwin-White, *The Letters of Pliny*, p. 629: “it is clear that two grades of local citizens existed at Apamea at this date, Greeks of the city and Romans of the colony”.

⁶² *JRS* 58 (1968), 218–224, 222: “This means simply that the unnamed emperor could merely have bestowed Roman citizenship on Dio’s maternal grandfather and mother, but in fact made them *coloni* of Apamea as well.”

⁶³ Millar, loc. cit.

⁶⁴ S. Mitchell, ‘Iconium and Ninica. Two Double Communities in Roman Asia Minor’, *Historia* 28 (1979), pp. 409–38, at p. 436.

⁶⁵ Mitchell, ‘Double Communities’, p. 417: “the evidence for the Caesarian colonies of Sinope and Heracleia Pontica strongly suggests that the Roman settlements did not cancel out but complemented the cities which already existed there”.

⁶⁶ Corsten, *Inschriften von Apameia*, p. 13f. (chapter “Apameia wird römische Kolonie”).

Mitchell's study focused on the cities of Iconium and Ninica, and the coinage of Iconium/Claudiconium in Lycaonia⁶⁷ indeed provides a most interesting parallel to Apamea: The city minted not only issues with Latin legends as *Col(onia) Iul(ia) Aug(usta) Iconi(ensium)*, but also Greek ones inscribed ΚΛΑΥΔΕΙΚΟΝΙΕΙΩΝ, under the Flavians.⁶⁸ Apparently, the colony and a local settlement existed side by side. There is, therefore, *a priori* no reason to doubt that a similar constitutional scheme might have been in operation in Apamea as well.

Coinage aside, close inspection of some of the literary sources dealing with Apamea can perhaps provide additional evidence for the correctness of the view held by Kubitschek and Sherwin-White concerning the constitutional status of the settlement. First, a somewhat mysterious passage in the "Natural History" of Pliny the Elder († AD 79), where he refers to the place as *Apamea, quae nunc Myrlea Colophoniorum* (5.143). This is an unexpected wording,⁶⁹ since the same author calls the settlement *colonia Apamena* elsewhere (5.149). It may, however, be telling to find the name "Myrlea" being used in a literary source of Flavian date. Would it be an overinterpretation of the passage to take it as a reference, not to the Roman colony, but to the Greek settlement which existed alongside the Roman, and which – on the evidence of the Claudian coin – continued to use the old name?

Three passages of Strabo help understanding of the process by which the *Colonia Iulia Concordia Apamea* came into being. According to him, the Apameans "received" a Roman colony: Οἱ δ' Ἀπαμεῖς ἀποικίαν ἐδέξαντο Ῥωμαίων (12.4.3 [564 C.]). The verb "δέχομαι" was obviously a technical term in this context, as comparison with Strabo's more explicit reports about the Roman colonies at Heraclea Pontica and Sinope shows. According to Strabo, Heraclea received a Roman colony "on a part of the city (*polis*) and of the territory belonging to it (*chora*)": ἐδέξατο ἀποικίαν Ῥωμαίων ἐπὶ μέρει τῆς πόλεως καὶ τῆς χώρας (12.3.6 [542 C.]). As the further narrative indicates, the two communities of the Greeks and the Romans existed there side by side after the colony's foundation. The establishment of the Roman colony at Sinope is described by Strabo in similar terms: Νυνὶ δὲ καὶ Ῥωμαίων ἀποικίαν δέδεκται καὶ μέρος τῆς πόλεως καὶ τῆς χώρας ἐκείνων ἐστὶ (12.3.11 [546 C.]).⁷⁰

On the basis of the literary evidence, it seems reasonable to assume that the deduction of the Roman colony at Apamea did not wipe out the pre-existing Greek settlement by simply replacing it, but that the Roman foundation occupied only a part of the latter's soil – as it was the case with some other Roman colonies, at least in Asia minor. From that point onwards, the two co-existing communities seem to have been separate entities juridically, with both of them theoretically being entitled to strike their own coinage. But Myrlea hardly ever seems to have made use of this privilege: as Sherwin-White correctly observed, "the practical difference between the

⁶⁷ Discussed by Mitchell, 'Double Communities', pp. 414–6.

⁶⁸ *RPC* 2, 1607–8 (Greek issues, with local types) and 1609–11 (Latin colonial issues, with 'Roman' types). See the brief discussion in *RPC* 2, pp. 6 and 232.

⁶⁹ Cp. Corsten, *Inschriften von Apameia*, p. 7 ("Plinius vertauscht allerdings die Reihenfolge der Namengebung").

⁷⁰ "Now [Sinope] received a colony of the Romans, and a part of the city and its territory belongs to them".

two communities was probably fast disappearing”,⁷¹ and obviously the importance of the *colonia* was constantly increasing. By the time of Trajan, the Roman colony will *de facto* already have become the successor of the Greek city of Apamea Myrlea. The choice of the original founding hero Myrlos as a reverse type for colonial coins in the second century AD can thus neatly be contextualized.

List of illustrations

Trajanic coins of Apamea in Bithynia (for detailed descriptions, technical data and further references see text)

- 1 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, Schürmann coll., inv.-no. 2512. Photo © Franziska Schmidt-Dick.
- 2 Paris, Bibliothèque nationale, Cabinet des médailles, no. 220. *Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 253, no. 42. Photo *Recueil* pl. XXXVIII, no. 13.
- 3 Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Münzkabinett <<http://www.smb.museum/ikmk/>>. Acc. 1928 Bernhard-Imhoof. Photo © Reinhard Saczewski.
- 4 CNG Electronic Auction 245 (1 December 2010), no. 256. Photo © CNG.

Supplementary material

- A Titus for Domitian, sestertius, eastern mint (*RIC* 2.1² 508): Lanz 128 (22 May 2006), 341 (26.15 g). This example illustrated in *RIC*.
- B Apamea in Bithynia, Antoninus Pius (*Rec. gén.* 1.2, p. 253, no. 45 = *RPC* online temp. no. 4720): Munich, Staatliche Münzsammlung (4.62 g; 12 h). Photo © Nicolai Kästner.
- C Sidon, Trajan (*SNG Cop.* 252): CNG Electronic Auction 160 (14 March 2007), 238 (9.68 g).

⁷¹ Sherwin-White, *The Letters of Pliny*, p. 629.

PLATE 14

1

2

3a (x1.5)

3

4

A

B

Ba (x1.5)

C

